

IOT PET-FEEDER WITH HOME SECURITY ROBOT

*¹Dr.Pampapathi BM, ²Apoorva K, ³Archana BK, ⁴Ashwini K

**¹Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, RYM Engineering College, Ballari, VTU Belagavi, Karnataka, India*

^{2,3,4}Student, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, RYM Engineering College, VTU Belagavi, Karnataka, India

Abstract: One of the serious issues in recent years has been the challenge of ensuring timely pet feeding and home security. The Pet Feeder and Home Security Robot is a multifunctional system designed to cater to the needs of pet owners while ensuring the security of their homes. In today's fast-paced world, pet owners often find it challenging to maintain regular feeding schedules for their pets while ensuring the safety of their homes. To address these challenges, this project proposes a novel solution that combines the functionalities of a pet feeder and a home security system into a single integrated robot. The robot serves as a cost-effective home security system, utilizing a Passive Infrared Sensor (PIR) for motion detection. The system utilizes Arduino microcontroller technology along with various sensors and actuators to automate the feeding process for pets and enhance home security through motion detection and alert mechanisms. By providing a convenient and efficient solution for pet care and home security, the Pet Feeder and Home Security Robot aims to improve the overall well-being and peace of mind of pet owners.

Keywords: Automatic Pet Feeder, Home Security, PIR sensor, Arduino microcontroller technology

1. INTRODUCTION

Owning a pet is a rewarding experience that brings joy, companionship, and a sense of responsibility to individuals and families. Pets quickly become cherished members of the household, and their well-being is a top priority for pet owners. One of the primary responsibilities of pet ownership is ensuring that pets are fed regularly and provided with adequate nutrition. However, maintaining consistent feeding schedules can be challenging, especially for pet owners with busy lifestyles or irregular work schedules. In addition to pet care responsibilities, homeowners also face the ongoing challenge of ensuring the safety and security of their homes. With the rise of crime and security threats in many communities, homeowners are increasingly seeking ways to enhance the security of their properties and protect their loved ones and valuables from potential intruders. Recognizing the need for innovative solutions to address these dual challenges, this project proposes the development of a pet feeder and a home security robot. This robot combines the functionalities of a pet feeder and a home security system into a single integrated device, offering pet owners a convenient and efficient solution to manage both their pets' needs and home security concerns.

The Pet Feeder and Home Security Robot will be equipped with advanced features and capabilities to automate the feeding process for pets and enhance home security through real-time monitoring and alert mechanisms. The robot will utilize Arduino microcontroller technology as the central processing unit, along with a range of sensors and actuators, including motors, motor drivers, RTC (Real-Time Clock) modules, servo motors, and motion sensors. The pet feeder functionality of the robot will enable pet owners to program feeding schedules for their pets, ensuring that they receive food at regular intervals, even when the owners are away from home. The system will utilize the RTC module to keep track of time and activate the servo motor to dispense the appropriate amount of food into the pet's feeding bowl according to the programmed schedule. In addition to the pet feeder functionality, the robot will also incorporate home security features to detect and respond to potential security threats.

The motion sensor will continuously monitor the surrounding area for any signs of motion or activity. If motion is detected, the robot will trigger an alert mechanism to notify the homeowner of the potential

intrusion, allowing them to take appropriate action to protect their home and property. Overall, the Pet Feeder and Home Security Robot aims to provide pet owners with a comprehensive solution that addresses both their pet care and home security needs. By combining advanced technology with innovative design, this project seeks to enhance the well-being and peace of mind of pet owners, allowing them to enjoy their pets while knowing that their homes are safe and secure for their pet care and home security needs. By combining advanced technology with innovative design, this project seeks to enhance the well-being and peace of mind of pet owners, allowing them to enjoy their pets while knowing that their homes are safe and secure.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In recent years, pet ownership has seen a significant increase, with many individuals choosing to welcome pets into their homes as beloved companions. However, with busy work schedules and other commitments, pet owners often face challenges in providing adequate care and attention to their pets throughout the day. One of the primary concerns for pet owners who work outside the home is ensuring that their pets receive proper care and attention in their absence. Unlike humans, pets cannot be left alone for extended periods without food, water, or companionship. This dilemma has led to the rise of innovative solutions to address the needs of pets left alone during the day.

Junyan Wang, Yuqian Wang, Miaomiao Wang, Jun Ma, and Haote Sun (2023) developed an automated pet feeder using Internet of Things (IoT) technology to address the challenge of caring for pets remotely and conveniently, especially in situations where pet owners are unable to be present due to busy lifestyles or unforeseen circumstances such as travel or emergencies. To tackle this issue, they proposed the design of a pet automatic timing feeder. The system comprises several key modules, including the STC89C52 MCU main control module, the LCD1602 LCD module for user interface, the ULN2003 driver module for motor control, the DS1302 clock module for accurate timekeeping, and the voice output module for auditory feedback. Together, these modules enable the feeder system to automate the feeding process for pets, allowing pet owners to remotely and conveniently provide food for their pets at regular intervals.

Ekta Jain, Sakshi Badwaik, Sampada Khirwadkar, Shruti Thakare, Mayur Uike, and Pankaj H. Chandankhade (2023) proposed a work and the goal is to create an autonomous pet feeding system based on the Internet of Things (IoT) that makes use of embedded systems technology. To prevent obesity and encourage good eating habits, this system is made to handle the problem of feeding pets when their owners are away from the house. It makes sure that pets receive meals on time and under control. Developing an embedded system-controlled feeding mechanism, integrating IoT connectivity for remote monitoring and control, implementing algorithms for feeding schedule management based on pet owners' preferences and dietary requirements, and integrating behavior monitoring sensors to train pets for scheduled meals. In addition, a user-friendly interface will be created so that owners of dogs can communicate with the system and keep an eye on their pet's behavior.

Prithviraj V and Sriharipriya K.C (2022) proposed research work that focuses on developing an IoT-based automated pet feeder system to address the challenge of feeding pets when pet owners are away from home. Recognizing the emotional attachment people have to their pets and the difficulty of maintaining feeding schedules in busy day-to-day schedules, their goal is to provide a solution that simplifies pet care for owners. The automated pet feeder system will allow pet owners to feed their pets remotely through Google Assistant ensuring that their pets receive timely meals even when the owners are not at home. This technology aims to make pet care more enjoyable and less stressful for owners, ultimately enabling more people to have pets in their homes without worrying about feeding issues.

P. N Vrishanka, Parimala Prabhakar, Devika Shet, and K Rupali (2021) developed an automated pet feeder using Internet of Things (IoT) technology to address the challenges faced by pet owners, particularly in ensuring regular and controlled feeding for their pets, while also promoting weight management and overall pet health.

Prudhvi Raj Budumuru, Santosh Chegondi, Leela Vamsi M, M Arjun; M Rohith, N Harikrishna (2022) proposed a smart radar security system that leverages radar technology to enhance surveillance

capabilities. This system utilizes radar sensors to detect and track movement, presence, and object classification in various environments, offering advantages over traditional security methods. The core functionality revolves around high-precision motion detection, providing accurate alerts whenever unauthorized movement is detected. The system incorporates Bluetooth technology for establishing a user interface and sending alerts to a mobile application, allowing users to receive real-time notifications on their smartphones or connected devices.

Pavan Kumar Sattaru, Khasim Vali Burugula, Rajasree Channagiri, S . Kavitha (2023) proposed work aims to address the pressing need for enhanced home security systems in light of the increasing risks of theft, burglary, and accidents. With the rise in home burglaries and fire incidents, there is a clear demand for advanced security solutions that provide continuous monitoring and protection. To meet this need, their research work focuses on designing and developing a novel smart home security system. Their system utilizes technological advancements to enable remote monitoring of home activities, allowing homeowners to detect and respond to unusual events from any location and at any time. Rishabh Bhardwaj, Raj Kothiyal, and Sachin Sharma (2023) proposed the implementation of an effective smart home security system. Recognizing security as an ongoing process, their study delves into analyzing current security issues and offering remedies to safeguard belongings and occupants against potential threats like break-ins and burglaries. They include utilizing PIR motion sensors for detection, employing the YOLO method for image identification captured by camera modules, and utilizing electromagnetism controlled by a Raspberry Pi for door opening. Additionally, cloud-based notifications will be provided to users regarding door-opening events, ensuring the safety and peace of mind of homeowners.

3. METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 System Design

The system design of the Pet Feeder and Home Security Robot project centers on integrating pet feeding and home security features seamlessly. Outlining the hardware and software components needed and ensuring compatibility among them. The implementation phase involves assembling the hardware components and programming the Arduino microcontroller to control the operation of the pet feeder module and home security module. Additionally, a user interface module is developed to provide intuitive controls and real-time status updates via a smartphone app using Bluetooth technology. Rigorous testing is then conducted to validate the functionality and reliability of each system component, including feeding schedules, motion detection, and user interface interaction.

It consists of key modules: the user interface for user-system interaction via a smartphone app, the control unit managing system operations using an Arduino microcontroller, functioning as the system's central processing unit, and orchestrating the interactions among various components. DC motors are utilized to drive mechanical actions within the pet feeder module, while a motor driver interfaces with the Arduino to regulate their operation. A Real-Time Clock (RTC) module ensures precise timing for pet feeding schedules. The servo motor controls the accurate dispensing of food into the pet's feeding bowl as per the programmed timetable. To bolster home security, a motion sensor detects any unauthorized movements within the premises, triggering the alert mechanism. Power is supplied to the system components either through batteries or an AC adapter, ensuring continuous functionality. Additionally, an enclosure safeguards the electronic elements, enhancing durability and safety. Furthermore, a Bluetooth module enables wireless communication with the user interface, typically a smartphone app, facilitating remote monitoring and control.

Fig(3.1) System Architecture

3.2 Flow Diagram

The flow control mechanism orchestrates the interaction between its components to ensure efficient pet feeding and home security monitoring. It begins with user inputs through the user interface module, where pet owners set feeding schedules and configure security settings via a smartphone app. Simultaneously, the pet feeder module, equipped with a Real-Time Clock (RTC) module, evaluates the programmed schedules to dispense food at the designated times using a servo motor. Meanwhile, the home security module, powered by a motion sensor, continuously monitors the surrounding area for any signs of motion. Upon detecting motion, the module triggers an alert mechanism, activating various notification methods such as audible alarms and remote notifications to inform the homeowner of potential intrusions. Through this coordinated flow control, the project ensures that both pet care and home security needs are met effectively, providing convenience and peace of mind to users.

Fig(3.2) Flow Diagram

3.3 Mechanical Design

The four-wheeled mechanism ensures that it feeds the pet in the given time interval. This design advantageously allows the robot to continue running enabling it to overcome obstacles. The robot gains traction solely due to its body weight.

A differential drive robot utilizes a simple locomotion system comprising four drive wheels. The drive wheels in each direction are attached to the body of the robot, with each independently controlled, enabling the robot's rotation and translation. Pure translation is achieved when all drive wheels have the same velocity (magnitude and direction), while pure rotation occurs when the velocities of both left and right-side drive wheels are the same in magnitude but with opposite directions.

Kinematic equations define the relationship between control commands and the corresponding space state. In a differential drive locomotion robot, these equations reflect the robot's position (x , y , θ) when the velocity of each drive wheel is controlled (V_{right} , V_{left}). Consequently, translational and rotational velocities can be expressed using the drive wheel velocities.

$$V = (V_{right} + V_{left})/2$$

$$\omega = (V_{right} - V_{left})/2L$$

Where L is the length of the drive wheel axis. The kinematic equations of a differential drive locomotion robot can be expressed as:

$$x' = (V_{right} + V_{left})/2 * \cos(\theta)$$

$$y' = (V_{right} + V_{left})/2 * \sin(\theta)$$

$$\theta' = (V_{right} - V_{left})/L$$

3.4 Mechanism

The entire body of the robot is composed of a square plate connected to four regular circular wheels, all of which are made of Polyvinylchloride (PVC). The view of the pet-feeding robot with the wheels is shown below:

Fig(3.4): Prototype of pet feeder

3.5 Graphical User Interface

This Arduino sketch combines several functionalities including Bluetooth communication, real-time clock (RTC) control, motor control, and intrusion detection using an infrared sensor. The interface can be given by:

```

22:13:19.453 no feed
22:13:19.453 0
22:13:19.453 current time:22:13
22:13:19.762 no feed
22:13:19.762 0
22:13:19.762 current time:22:13
22:13:20.044 no feed
22:13:20.044 0
22:13:20.044 current time:22:13
22:13:20.165 5
22:13:20.361 no feed
22:13:20.361 0
22:13:20.361 current time:22:13
22:13:20.656 no feed
22:13:20.656 0
22:13:20.656 current time:22:13
  
```

Fig(3.5):Graphical interface

A window is created with different buttons namely right, left, back, forward, stop, and timer. If the received Bluetooth data matches '1', the robot moves forward. For the '2' input the robot moves backward. For the '3', the robot turns right. For the '4', the robot turns left. If the received data is '5' the robot is stopped. Lastly, if the received data matches '6', the code sends a message "set time to feed" via Serial communication. These conditional statements provide a way to control the robot's movement and trigger specific actions based on the input received from the Bluetooth device.

4. RESULT

Upon the completion and implementation of the proposed system for the Pet Feeder and Home Security Robot, the following expected results are anticipated:

Successfully dispenses pet food at scheduled times: The robot successfully dispenses pet food at scheduled times or on command, ensuring that pets are fed even when their owners are away. The feeding mechanism accurately portions out the correct amount of food for each pet, preventing overfeeding or underfeeding.

Fig(4.1): Pet feeding dispenser

The security system detects and alerts homeowners. The motion sensor-based home security system integrated with the robot detects and triggers alert mechanisms to notify homeowners promptly of any unauthorized entry or suspicious activity within the home, enhancing overall security measures.

Fig(4.2): Security Sensor

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Pet Feeder and Home Security Robot provides pet owners with a complete solution that takes care of their demands for both home security and pet care. The robot gives owners piece of mind by monitoring houses for security risks and ensuring pets are fed regularly through creative design and cutting-edge technology. By combining advanced technology with innovative design, the project addresses the dual challenges faced by pet owners in maintaining regular feeding schedules for their pets while ensuring the safety of their homes. The system's ability to automate pet feeding schedules remotely via a smartphone app, coupled with real-time monitoring of home security using motion sensors, offers unparalleled convenience and peace of mind to users. Overall, the project's success in enhancing the well-being and security of both pets and homeowners.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Hari N. Khatavkar, Rahul S. Kini, Suyash K. Pandey, and Vaibhav V. Gijare, "Intelligent Food Dispenser (IFD)", published by IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN), pp. 65-70, 2019.
- [2] Taivalasaari and T. Mikkonen, "On the development of IoT systems", 2018 Third International Conference on Fog and Mobile Edge Computing (FMEC), pp. 13-19, 2018.
- [3] Hari N. Khatavkar, Rahul S. Kini, Suyash K. Pandey, and Vaibhav V. Gijare, "Intelligent Food Dispenser (IFD)", 2019.
- [4] Ma and N. Guo, "Design of Remote Pet Feeding System Based on ARM", 2020 Chinese Automation Congress (CAC), pp. 1702-1704, 2020.
- [5] Kalbande Vaishnavi, Gautami Tikale, Rahul Agrawal, Swati Sorte, Laxman Thakre and Ganesh Khekare, "Design and Implementation of Motion Sensing Security System", 2022 3rd International Conference on Electronics and Sustainable Communication Systems (ICESC), pp. 612-517, 2022.

- [6] Koley Soumallya, Sneha Srimani, Debanjana Nandy, Pratik Pal, Samriddha Biswas, and Indranath Sarkar, "Smart Pet Feeder", Journal of Physics: Conference Series, vol. 1797, no. 1, pp. 012018, 2021
- [7] S. N. R. R. A. S. Raveena Ishalavath M, Design and Development of an Automated Floor for domestic application, Mysuru: International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT), 2020.
- [8] A. U. Pranav Iyengar, "Development of Autonomous Indoor Floor", International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE), vol. 11, no. 3, 2022.
- [9] M. Sunitha, P. V. S. S. Datta Vinay, V. S. N. Lokesh, and B. D. Kumar, "IP Based Surveillance Robot Using IOT", 2020 Fourth International Conference on I-SMAC (IoT in Social Mobile Analytics and Cloud) (iSMAC), pp. 337-342, 2020.
- [10] G. Suci, S. Stefanescu, C. Beceanu, and M. Ceaparu, "WebRTC role in real-time communication and video conferencing" in 2020 Global Internet of Things Summit (GIoTS), IEEE, pp. 1-6, June 2020.
- [11] Ekta Jain, Sakshi Badwaik, Sampadha Khirwadkar, Shruthi Thakare "Design of smart pet food dispenser using Embedded system" 2023 International Conference on Emerging Smart Computing and Informatics (ESCI), 19 April 2023
- [12] PN Vrishanka, Parimala Prabhakar, Devika Shet, K Rupali "Automated Pet Feeder using IoT", 2021 IEEE International Conference on Mobile Networks and Wireless Communications (ICMNC), 26 January 2022
- [13] Tannop Sangvanloy, Kingkarn Sookhanphibarn "Automatic Pet Food Dispenser by using Internet of Things (IoT)", 2020 IEEE 2nd Global Conference on Life Sciences and Technologies (LifeTech), 30 April 2020
- [14] R. C. Luo and K. L. Su, "Autonomous Fire-Detection System Using Adaptive Sensory Fusion for Intelligent Security Robot", IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 274-281, June 2007
- [15] Y. Chen, B. Leighton, H. Zhu, X. Ke, S. Liu and L. Zhao, "Submap-Based Indoor Navigation System for the Fetch Robot", IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 81479-81491, 2020.
- [16] Pampapathi B M , Nageswara Guptha M , M S Hema , "Towards an effective deep learning-based intrusion detection system in the internet of things" , in Telematics and Informatics Reports Journal- May 2022 , <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.teler.2022.100009>.
- [17] Pampapathi, Mr, Komal Singh, V. Madhavi, Madhu B. Yallaraddi, and Mangala Desai. "Smart band for women safety using Internet of Things (IoT)." IJARCCCE 7, no. 3 (2018): 120-123.
- [18] Pampapathi B M , Dr. Nageswara Guptha M , Mahantesh H M , "Survey on Data Communication Frameworks in IoT" , UGC care approved International Journal of Management, Technology and Engineering (IJMTE) , Volume IX , Issue VI , ISSN NO: 2249-7455 in June 2019 , <https://16.10089.IJMTE.2019.V9I6.19.29002>.
- [19] Pampapathi B M , Nageswara Guptha M , M S Hema , "Malicious Node Detection and Energy-aware Optimal Routing in Wireless Sensor Networks using CD-LVQ and BMSSO Algorithms" in The Journal of Huazhong University of Science and Technology , Volume 50 , Issue 03.- March 2021- <http://hustjournal.com/vol50mar-2/>.

[20] Pampapathi B M , Nageswara Guptha M , M S Hema , “Energy Efficient Data Distribution on Cloud With Optimal Routing Path Based Congestion Control in WSN Environment” in Journal of University of Shanghai for Science and Technology(JUSST), Volume 23, Issue 8, August 2021, <https://doi.org/10.51201/JUSST/21/08409>.

[21] Pampapathi B M , Chandana Murthy , Supriya Kumar , Pooja M , Supriya K “Survey on IOT Based Medical Box for Elderly People” in International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering (IJATCSE) ISSN 2278-3091, Vol.10 No.3 (May – June 2021 issue), <https://doi.org/10.30534/ijatcse/2021/531032021>.

[22] Pampapathi B M, A Madhuri, Chennareddy Nikhil, Amar Gouda Patil “Water Monitoring And Purification Of Waste Water For Agriculture Using Iot” in Journal For Basic Sciences Volume 23, Issue 4, 2023 , <https://doi.org/10.37896/JBSV23.4/2050>.

[23] Pampapathi B M, Mohammad Moshin P , Mohammed Kareemuddin Saqlain, Prajwal Marthur, K Md Ibrahim hussain “Wireless Fire Detection Systems Using Iot” in NOVYI MIR Research Journal , Volume 8 Issue 4 2023 <https://doi.org/10.10098.NMRJ.2022.V8I4.256342.37538>.

[24] Pampapathi B M , Shruthi S M,” Detection and Classification of Phishing Websites Using Machine Learning” , in Journal Of Technology - Aug 2023 - Issn No:1012-3407 , Vol 13, Issue 8,D.O.I- <https://10.61350/v13-105368>.